

DASSI DATA PRESERVATION POLICY

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1. Policy objectives

Data Archive for Social Sciences in Italy (DASSI) is a research infrastructure aimed at preserving and sharing data produced in the social sciences. This document describes the principles and procedures used in the data archiving process and the strategy adopted for the long-term preservation of these resources.

In particular, the preservation policy describes all the measures taken by DASSI to guarantee permanent access to the research data acquired, the responsibilities assumed in their management and the strategy implemented to ensure their retrievability and future reuse.

The document is addressed to data producers, funders, users and anyone interested in using the data archived at DASSI. With this policy, the archive demonstrates that it is aware of the main challenges of digital preservation and that it has the necessary skills to deal with them appropriately, treating the data with the necessary care and, where necessary, adapting its workflows to ensure the usability and correct interpretation of these resources.

The Preservation Policy will be reviewed every three years in order to adapt appropriately to changes in the technical and research environment in which the infrastructure operates. Its periodic review will allow for the implementation of any necessary measures for data protection and compliance with national and international standards developed in the field of digital preservation, including the requirements for obtaining a trusted certification. An appropriate preservation policy will also enable the archive to meet the expectations of its user community, to monitor technological evolution and the risk of obsolescence of digital material, to improve its resource preservation strategies and to ensure greater quality in all processes and work phases.

2. Organisational framework

DASSI is a research infrastructure created by the University of Milan-Bicocca (UNIMIB) and the National Research Council (CNR). Since 2021, it has been recognised by the Ministry of University and Research (MUR) as the Italian National Service Provider of the European CESSDA ERIC infrastructure.

2.1. Mission

The main objective of DASSI is to support the scientific community by enabling high quality research in the social sciences. Specifically, DASSI works to ensure the long-term preservation and sharing of research data according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. DASSI's activities are aimed at enhancing the value of research data, improving its visibility and accessibility, and accurately documenting the entire data curation process in order to enable the scientific community to use these resources correctly and independently (see Statute).

Digital preservation is therefore a crucial aspect of DASSI's activities, as it enables it to achieve its main objective, which is to actively support Italian social science research in the long term.

2.2. Scope of the collection

DASSI addresses the social sciences in general and promotes the deposit of research data produced by all researchers belonging to this scientific field.

The archive acquires research data relating to Italian society (i.e. data relating to Italy or data from other countries other than Italy in a comparative perspective) or collected by Italian researchers.

The DASSI Data Acquisition Policy defines criteria for the selection and evaluation of archived data. These criteria are mainly related to the richness, exhaustiveness and completeness of the documentation provided, the accessibility of the data (both in terms of integrity and format) and the degree of compliance with ethical and legal principles.

2.3. Designated Community

The primary Designated Community of DASSI consists of social science researchers (academic and non-academic) who can take on the role of both data providers (i.e. those who create the data) and end-users (i.e. those who use the data created by others). The secondary Designated Community includes students, teachers, educators, politicians, media representatives, journalists, citizens or anyone who wants to use the archived data, and who therefore acts as an end-user (see Statute).

The data preservation policy defines the best strategies to meet the needs of the Designated Community, which is periodically monitored in order to adapt the policy to the most significant changes, both technological (e.g. formats or software used by users) and substantive (e.g. assessing the impact of changes in the legal framework, such as

the introduction of the GDPR). DASSI acts to ensure that data are fully used and correctly interpreted by its user community.

2.4. Access

The data archived at DASSI can be accessed via the [Dataverse platform](#), where the archive's online catalogue is published. The catalogue contains an up-to-date list of *studies*, each with its associated datasets, documentation and metadata. The platform allows free access to all the materials of each study, according to the licences set by the owner. Dataverse also allows the assignment of persistent identifiers (DOIs) for each archived study. The DOI allows the data and its different versions to be uniquely and permanently identified and cited.

The archive prepares the materials made available to users according to the needs of the target community and in the formats most suitable for their use.

DASSI also concludes specific agreements with data depositors and users in order to guarantee the respect of rights of use and intellectual property rights. These agreements are based on the principles of Open Access and the Creative Commons licences.

In addition to the data distribution platform, the archive uses a dedicated server to display the metadata for each study. The server, based on the [Data Documentation Initiative \(DDI\) metadata standard](#), enables automated metadata harvesting using the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).

3. Preservation challenges

The archive is responsible for the long-term preservation of the data. One of the main challenges in achieving this goal is the *usability* and *accessibility* of these resources: DASSI ensures that the archived data are identifiable and searchable through its online catalogue, uniquely citable through a persistent identifier (DOI), freely and directly downloadable through its distribution platform, and efficiently retrievable when needed.

DASSI also guarantees the *reliability* and *authenticity* of the distributed data, ensuring that they are consistent with what they refer to, documenting any transformation that may be necessary for their correct use, verifying the identity of those who created them and when they were created. The preservation of digital material is also linked to the dependency on the software used to create the data. In order to guarantee the long-term usability of the data, it is often necessary to create a version in a format different from the original. In these cases, DASSI guarantees the authenticity of the new version by

documenting all the actions carried out and by validating the conformity of the content of the version created, ensuring that it has not been modified.

Another preservation challenge concerns the long-term *comprehensibility* of the data, i.e. ensuring that they can be correctly interpreted in the future. The archive is responsible for creating and maintaining a metadata system that provides detailed and standardised descriptions. This will ensure easy and immediate interpretation of the data, increase its interoperability and ensure harmonisation with other similar resources.

The preservation procedures adopted by DASSI also guarantee adequate *protection* of digital resources and an appropriate level of *security*. The archive applies a specific data backup and security strategy to facilitate rapid data recovery in case of need, and takes suitable measures to control access to its IT infrastructure.

Digital preservation also has to deal with the effects of rapid *technological change*. Technical and operational changes (e.g. in hardware, software, file formats, etc.) put the use of digital data at risk. DASSI regularly monitors technological developments and adopts an appropriate migration strategy to ensure access and correct use of the data in the long term.

Finally, digital preservation poses important challenges in terms of rights of use, privacy and intellectual property, which must be adequately protected. DASSI provides for the conclusion of specific agreements with the holder of these rights, ensuring that the archive has the necessary permissions to make the data available for re-use, and to perform any format transformations and/or migrations for preservation purposes.

In general terms, DASSI operates within the following framework:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016/679)
- Personal Data Protection Code (196/2003), adapted to the GDPR in 2018
- Prescriptions concerning the processing of personal data for scientific research purposes (Garante per la protezione dei dati personali, 2016)
- Deontological rules for processing for statistical or scientific research purposes (Garante per la protezione dei dati personali, 2018)

4. Data preservation strategy

4.1. Principles

In carrying out its activities, DASSI uses standards and models recognised by the international community. First and foremost, research data are managed in accordance with the FAIR principles, i.e. by directing activities in such a way that these resources are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable by anyone, autonomously and independently.

The archive also adopts the Open Archival Information System (OAIS) reference model to define the processes, procedures and actions required for the long-term preservation and accessibility of data.

Figure 1: OAIS Functional Model (en).svg, Mathieualexhache (original work); Mess (SVG conversion & English translation), CC BY-SA 4.0, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0>, via Wikimedia Commons. Retrieved 04/07/2024 from [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:OAIS_Functional_Model_\(en\).svg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:OAIS_Functional_Model_(en).svg)

Compliance with the OAIS model is also one of the obligations of the national Service Providers of the CESSDA infrastructure, of which DASSI is a member. In accordance with this model, the archive manages the creation and preservation of three information packages: the *Submission Information Package (SIP)*, the *Archival Information Package*

(AIP) and the *Dissemination Information Package (DIP)*. During the process, all transformations made to the data are documented in detail to ensure their proper preservation and authenticity. All data documentation is accessible to users in the form of metadata based on a recognised and widely accepted standard in the social sciences (DDI). The archive also identifies the most suitable data file formats to meet the challenges of long-term preservation, for example by avoiding proprietary, obsolete or rarely used formats. DASSI aims to be recognised as a Trustworthy Data Repository (TDR) for its Designated Community (primarily users and data depositors). To this end, procedures and workflows are regularly reviewed and adapted, and a self-assessment is carried out to verify compliance with the requirements necessary to obtain the [CoreTrustSeal](#) certification.

4.2. Strategy implementation

The OAIS model provides the framework for managing and implementing the steps of the archiving process. This model allows DASSI to plan and optimise its activities and to harmonise its procedures with those of other international organisations working in the same field.

Figure 2: DASSI OAIS Model

The OAIS model used by DASSI provides for a preliminary phase to the actual archiving, called *pre-ingest*. During this phase, the archive carries out two important activities: it provides support to the data producer, and it evaluates the material to be deposited. In the first case, DASSI makes available guidelines and other documents aimed at the proper preparation of data for deposit. These materials mainly concern the format of accepted data, anonymisation procedures and descriptive information needed to correctly contextualise the data. Archive staff will also provide assistance on ethical and legal issues (e.g. related to data ownership, informed consent, licence for use, etc.). At this stage, the *deposit agreement* is signed, in which the depositor grants the archive a licence to use the data, the actions that can be taken on the data and the end-user licence.

During the pre-ingest, DASSI also carries out an *appraisal* of the data to be deposited. In accordance with the Data Acquisition Policy, the archive checks that the acceptance criteria are met, i.e. that the data are well documented, anonymised, deposited in the recommended formats, checks for corruption and completeness of the data, and validates authenticity. If the deposit requirements are met, the archive will accept the material provided by the producer, which will form the SIP package. This package then preserves the version of the material in its original format.

The *ingest* phase includes the main *data curation* activities. During this phase, the archive checks, transforms and preserves the deposited materials, creates the associated metadata, and prepares the data and documentation for distribution to users. Specifically, the AIP and DIP packages are created during this stage, as well as metadata according to the DASSI Metadata Model (DaMM). The archive staff carry out data quality checks, identify the properties to be preserved, prepare the documents that will accompany the data (e.g. survey instruments, methodological notes, codebooks for quantitative data or data lists for qualitative data, etc.) and convert the file formats for long-term preservation. The original version of the data (SIP) is considered to be the only 'integral copy', while the archiving (AIP) and dissemination (DIP) versions are considered to be authentic and the trace of any changes made to the SIP is saved and archived. In addition to being carefully documented, all data transformations are also shared with the depositor. DASSI always distributes the archived data in an open format, providing possible scripts for import into the main analysis software used by the Designated Community. The metadata model (DaMM) is based on the DDI standard and is built according to the [CESSDA Metadata Model \(CMM\)](#). DASSI manages its metadata through a specific database that allows it to collect the main information useful for a correct understanding of the data

used in the social sciences: information on the study in which the data were produced, on the people involved in their production (author/creator, collaborators, etc.), on the main methodological characteristics (sampling, data collection techniques, etc.), on the temporal and territorial coverage of the data, on the conditions of access and use, and on the documents accompanying the data. Most of the necessary information is provided directly by the data producer and checked by the archive staff, who also take care of any missing metadata.

The *data management* phase accompanies and constantly interacts with the Ingest phase, managing the creation of metadata and the transformation of data and documentation. Specifically, Data Management guarantees the authenticity and integrity of the data by generating the checksums for each file, controls the versioning of the data and manages the documentation of changes, ensuring their traceability, manages and maintains the metadata system and its interfaces, and coordinates the operation of the various work platforms.

The *archival storage* phase is responsible for preserving the information packages (SIP, AIP and DIP) produced during the process. DASSI's archive storage system guarantees the accessibility, permanent preservation and retrieval of the resources created. The system, which is constantly monitored and updated, is based on a highly redundant Fibre Channel technology infrastructure. In addition to the reliability guaranteed by RAID-type mechanisms, the storage is configured in a stretched cluster mode. This means that data is mirrored across two storage locations in two different data centres. Data accessibility is guaranteed even if only one of the two data centres is active. In addition to the reliability guaranteed by the storage, there is a backup system on the system that makes an incremental copy of the data every night on a tape system.

Finally, the *access phase* deals with data distribution and user requests. In this phase, the archive is responsible for making the DIP available through the distribution platform (Dataverse), making the data visible and searchable through its online catalogue, enabling the harvesting of metadata, managing the interaction with users, and controlling any access to the released data with specific usage restrictions. Each published study is assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) directly from the distribution platform. Before publishing data via its online catalogue, DASSI informs the depositor of all the work carried out and shares the materials created.

The OAIS model therefore ensures data preservation through a strategy based on *normalisation* and *migration*. Digital material formats are particularly affected by the risk of obsolescence due to frequent changes in hardware and software. For this reason,

the archive defines a list of accepted file formats, i.e. those that offer better guarantees of usability, accessibility and long-term sustainability. In selecting these formats, DASSI refers to international best practices and gives preference to non-proprietary, open and documented, unencrypted and uncompressed formats. In addition, the format varies according to the type of data involved (quantitative, qualitative, numerical, textual, images, video, etc.). The list of formats accepted by the archive can be found in the Data Acquisition Policy and is made available in the data deposit guidelines. *Preservation planning* includes periodic review of the selected formats to assess their suitability for long-term preservation. Where necessary, DASSI will migrate any obsolete or unsuitable formats to new, more sustainable formats to ensure the future reusability of the data. Each format migration path is documented and validated to reduce the risk of information loss. However, the original format is retained to ensure the principle of reversibility, i.e. the ability to revert to an earlier version after migration. Each update of the list also includes a review of all related policies and is published on the DASSI website to inform its community.

4.3. Technical Infrastructure

To manage the archiving process, a modular infrastructure has been implemented, mainly based on the open source R software used by DASSI staff for data and documentation management. The metadata of the study are entered using a graphical interface developed in-house, which reports the information according to the DASSI Metadata Model (DaMM). Metadata are collected according to CESSDA requirements and, where relevant, controlled vocabularies provided by the same European infrastructure are used. All information is stored in a database that is regularly backed up. The database is accessed via a REST API: this strategy allows metadata to be read and written at any stage of the ingest process. The API also allows metadata to be exported in various formats, notably DDI and JSON for import into the Dataverse platform (see below). The same APIs are also used to import bibliographic information, which is managed within the Zotero platform.

The data, metadata and documentation of the studies are published within the Dataverse platform, installed *on premises* on servers managed directly by the CNR. The metadata, exported in DDI XML format, are also published within an OAI-PMH server, also managed by the CNR, which allows *harvesting* by external aggregators.

Access to part of the technical infrastructure (API, database, graphical interface) is only allowed via a VPN managed by the CNR, and any activity requires authentication by

the user. Only the Dataverse and OAI-PMH server services are externally available and accessible to DASSI users.

The services are provided by the virtualisation infrastructure running in the CNR data centre in Rome. The hosts on which the virtual machines run are divided into two machine rooms, each with its own power supply and cooling. Virtual machines can be migrated to any of the hosts. This migration can be done automatically (in the event of a host failure or according to the host's overload policy) or manually (e.g. when a host needs to be serviced). Migration takes place without disrupting the virtual machine. Storage is provided using Fibre Channel technology. There are two independent fabrics in the service centre that connect the storage to the hosts. The storage is virtualised and automatically duplicated weekly in the two machine rooms. In this way, a failure in one of the two machine rooms does not affect service delivery. Physical access to the systems is restricted to authorised staff of the ICT Office in Rome and through badge-based access control.

4.4. Monitoring and review

The preservation policy will be reviewed and, if necessary, updated every three years to ensure the continued relevance of the archive's digital preservation objectives and procedures, to identify any weaknesses or necessary changes, and to adapt it to potential changes - both technological and related to the scientific research environment - that may occur over time.

To this end, DASSI carries out continuous monitoring at several levels:

- monitor of the target community for changes - including technological changes - that may affect the archive's activities. An example is the data formats most commonly used by users to carry out their work. Monitoring will be done through the contacts that DASSI establishes with its own reference community (during the data acquisition phase, participation in research projects, conferences, training or support activities, etc.) or through discussions with other research infrastructures, national or international, scientific associations or other stakeholders
- monitoring technological changes, mainly by checking the risk of obsolescence of the formats accepted and managed by the archive (see 4.2) and the correct functioning of the technical infrastructure, i.e. the archiving, security and backup systems and the connection between the different parts that make up the technological architecture of DASSI (see 4.3)

- monitoring the impact of legislative and/or regulatory changes on the activities of the archive. This level includes monitoring changes in legislation – both at national and international level – that affect data management and production (e.g. data protection legislation), changes in codes of ethics and/or deontology, or changes in the principles guiding scientific research practices (e.g. the introduction of the FAIR or open science principles, which have led to significant changes in both data collection procedures and data management)
- monitoring changes that have a direct impact on DASSI's work, such as the development or modification of standards used, international best practices or the introduction of new business management tools.

5. Roles and responsibilities

DASSI has a distributed organisational structure consisting of two integrated units: *Data Curation*, which deals with all activities related to the acquisition and management of data for research; and *e-Research Infrastructure*, which coordinates all activities related to the preservation, access and dissemination of data for research, providing appropriate technical solutions to these needs. The two units operate within the partnership established between the University of Milano-Bicocca and the National Research Council: the *Data Curation* unit is coordinated by UNIMIB, while the *e-Research Infrastructure* unit is coordinated by CNR. The staff involved in the activities envisaged by DASSI can belong to either of the two partner institutions, with a view to full collaboration between them.

The coordination of the operational units is ensured by the Management and Coordination Committee (Italian acronym CGC), composed of members from the partner institutions, which coordinates and manages all the activities of the archive. Within the framework of this policy, the CGC is responsible for the definition and implementation of the policy, the *Data Curation* unit is responsible for the implementation of the strategy described (see 4.2), and the *e-Research Infrastructure* unit is responsible for the technical infrastructure (see 4.3).

All staff working in the archive shall actively participate in the implementation of the data preservation policy according to their roles and responsibilities. The staff involved must be up-to-date on the latest developments in the field of digital preservation, and are therefore encouraged to attend courses, conferences and other training events in order to further develop their knowledge and skills. DASSI will ensure that internal manuals

describing the archiving procedures and the necessary technical tools are prepared in a comprehensive and detailed manner and made available to all archive staff.

6. Related documents

- DASSI Statute
- DASSI Data acquisition policy
- DASSI Deposit Agreement
- CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025
- DASSI Metadata Model (DaMM)

The original of this document was drawn up in the Italian language. The Italian version is the authentic version and shall prevail over the English version in all matters of interpretation and construction.